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ACCESSIBLE DIGITAL LABORATORY BASED ON ARDUINO MEGA 2560 PLATFORM FOR PHYSICS TEACHING EXPERIMENT

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Annotation. The article shows the possibility of creating a modern digital laboratory based on the Arduino MEGA 2560 microcontroller platform for demonstration and laboratory physics experiment in the joint project activity of school teachers and students.

Key words: Arduino MEGA 2560 microcontroller board, digital physics laboratory, digital sensors, full-scale computer experiment in physics.

FIZIKA O'QITISH TAJRIBASI UCHUN ARDUINO MEGA 2560 PLATFORMASI ASOSIDA QULAY RAQAMLI LABORATORIYA

Annotatsiya. Maqolada maktab o'qituvchilari va o'quvchilarining qo'shma loyiha faoliyatida namoyish-laboratoriya fizikasi eksperimentini o'tkazish uchun Arduino MEGA 2560 mikrokontroller platformasi asosida zamonaviy raqamli laboratoriya yaratish imkoniyati ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Arduino MEGA 2560 mikrokontroller kengashi, raqamli fizika laboratoriyasi, raqamli sensorlar, fizikada to'liq hajmli kompyuter eksperimenti.

ДОСТУПНАЯ ЦИФРОВАЯ ЛАБОРАТОРИЯ НА БАЗЕ ПЛАТФОРМЫ ARDUINO MEGA 2560 ДЛЯ ПРОВЕДЕНИЯ ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТА ПО ОБУЧЕНИЮ ФИЗИКЕ

Аннотация. В статье показана возможность создания современной цифровой лаборатории на базе микроконтроллерной платформы Arduino MEGA 2560 для проведения демонстрационного и лабораторного эксперимента по физике в совместной проектной деятельности школьных учителей и учащихся.

Ключевые слова: плата микроконтроллера Arduino MEGA 2560, лаборатория цифровой физики, цифровые сенсоры, натурный компьютерный эксперимент по физике.

Their quality and capabilities largely determine the methodology of the experiment and the reliability of the results obtained. New approaches to conducting laboratory physical experiments at physics lessons, as well as in the organization of research and project work of schoolchildren opens the use of available microcontrollers in educational devices.

Microcontrollers are widely used in modern technology and electronics to control all types of systems and devices. Microcontrollers are used in all modern household appliances, robotics, medical devices, automobiles and many other areas, so familiarity and studying the principles of operation, capabilities and applications of microcontrollers is an essential element of schoolchildren's education.

An important source of learning cognition in school physics teaching is a learning experiment [1]. The importance and practical value of experimentation for students is that it reflects a scientific approach to the study of physical phenomena [2].

To increase students' interest in learning experiments, it is possible, for example, to develop learning laboratories with the use of available microcontrollers. [3,4,5] in the framework of additional education of technical direction. This article discusses in detail the possibility of creating in school conditions an analog of a computer laboratory based on the Arduino platform *MEGA* 2560, which we discussed

earlier in the report [6] and is more advanced in comparison with the one considered in the article [7]. The main difference between the Arduino MEGA 2560 microcontroller board and Arduino UNO is the presence of more pins, which allows connecting more sensors and actuators.

Previously created programs for the devices were separate sketches, which had to be loaded into the controller each time before the experiment when working with different sensors. This resulted in a noticeable time delay.

Fig. 1. General view of the device [6]

Currently, a program has been developed on the basis of the Arduino MEGA 2560 microcontroller board, which is able to combine all developed mini programs (functions) to different sensors and measuring devices and integrate them into one common program. The program structure built in this way allows the placement of mini programs for controlling a large number of different sensors, which the student can select depending on the type of connected device.

To conduct the experiment, it is enough to run a program in the PascalABC.NET, Python or Processing environment (in our case they are used for displaying information), and the mini program that is required to work with the sensor is selected using the encoder. For convenience, the names of the functions that provide the operation of the connected devices are printed on the display screen when the encoder is rotated. If you plan to use an Excel spreadsheet, you must start the Arduino-IDE development environment and enter the Serial Monitor.

Fig. 1 shows a general view of the described device, and Fig. 2 shows a general diagram of the loops and connected modules to the Arduino MEGA 2560 microcontroller board.

Figure 2. General diagram of loops and connected modules to the Arduino MEGA 2560 microcontroller board [6]

The device design includes five modules - a stable frequency pulse generator, a voltmeter based on ADC K1113PV1, a photo sensor unit, a counter-frequency meter and a radio module NRF24L01+. All modules are controlled by the Arduino MEGA 2560 microcontroller board.

The generator is designed to produce rectangular pulses of stable frequency, allowing to measure with high enough accuracy the duration of time intervals, period and frequency of electrical pulses by the method of their counting. The desired

frequency is selected automatically by the program using the built-in multiplexer K155KP7.

The use of ADC K1113PV1 allows to measure unipolar voltage up to 10 V and bipolar voltage up to ± 5 B. The voltmeter allows voltage measurement on two channels.

The block of photo sensors is used to determine speed, acceleration, obtain motion graphs, period and frequency of disk rotation. The primary converters of mechanical types of motion into electrical ones are built-in photo sensors.

The counter-frequency meter is designed to measure the frequency, period and duration of electrical pulses of rectangular shape. The program also includes a mode of counting electrical impulses, for example, to measure short time intervals of shading of photo sensors. The counter-frequency meter is based on binary-decimal counters K155HE5 [8].

The NRF24L01 + radio module is designed for receiving and transmitting data via radio channel, which provides wireless communication between the controller, various sensors and instruments of physical quantities. The radio module operates at a frequency of 2.4 GHz. The NRF24L01+ communication module contains both a receiver and a transmitter. The radio module can be replaced by an ESP8266 Wi Fi module or a blue tooth module. *HC – 06*.

The designed and manufactured device is used in demonstration and laboratory experiments in teaching physics. The whole list of functions currently available is presented in Table 1, the use of which provides a faster way to select the desired function. Method of their counting. The desired frequency is selected automatically by the program using the built-in multiplexer K155KP7.

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No	Program name	Brief explanation of the measured value	program
			PascalABC.NET
1	Mayatnik	Pendulum oscillations, graphing the coordinate and velocity of an oscillating body in Excel spreadsheets	serial port monitor, Excel spreadsheet
2	dynamometer 50	Electronic dynamometer with 50 H limit	dynamometer_50H_MEGA
3	dynamometer 10	Electronic dynamometer with 10 H limit	dynamometer_10H_MEGA
4	Disk speed	Measuring the rotational speed of a point on a disk	Time MEGA
5	Kinematika_1	Measuring the crossing time of photo sensors at two different points (single photo sensor method)	kinematics_1_MEGA
6	kinematika_3	Plotting coordinate and displacement in Excel spreadsheets	serial port monitor, Excel spreadsheet
7	ultrasound HC	Measurement of sound wave propagation velocity in gaseous media by ultrasonic transducer	
8	HC-SRO4	ultrasound HC	
9	vesy 300 gr	Measuring body weight on electronic scales up to 300 g	scale_300g_MEGA
10	magnetometer	Measurement of magnetic field induction with Hall sensor SS495, magnetic field induction superposition principle	magnetometer
11	VI_25V	Voltage and current measurement by digital sensor ADS1115	ampere_volt_2K_MEGA
12	chastotal	Measuring the frequency of electrical pulses. Measuring range 1-65535 Hz	Frequency MEGA
13	Ultra sound	Measurement of sound wave velocity in liquids and solids	Ultra sound

Table 1

The NRF24L01 + radio module is designed for receiving and transmitting data via radio channel, which provides wireless communication between the controller, various sensors and instruments of physical quantities. The radio module operates at a frequency of 2.4 GHz. The NRF24L01+ communication module contains both a receiver and a transmitter. The radio module can be replaced by an ESP8266 Wi Fi module or a blue tooth module. *HC – 06*.

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